

INSTRUCTIONAL INFORMATION

The following module template has been developed as part of Work Package 7 of the EU-funded GoGreen project. The module is designed in a skeletal format to allow for broad adaptation to a wide range of existing curricula and professional development schemes. To enhance flexibility, the module is divided into theme blocks with suggested content, assessments, and activities. The template has been constructed to serve as foundational material for curriculum development or course integration.

INTENDED AUDIENCE

This module may be adapted for the instruction of conservation, conservation science, and the broader cultural heritage sector at the undergraduate, postgraduate, and professional level. The activities and assessments of this module have been developed for both group and individual audiences.

MODULE DELIVERY

Content in this module supports in-person, hybrid, or virtual learning. The following online resources may be used for hybrid or virtual module instruction.

1. <https://padlet.com/>
2. <https://whiteboard.microsoft.com>
3. <https://www.mural.co/>

For optimal instructional delivery, this module benefits from access to case studies either from the suggested literature or from personal/local contexts.

PRE-REQUISITE KNOWLEDGE

Prior to undertaking the module, module-takers should be familiar with the following topics which may be gained from previous coursework or complementary GoGreen modules:

1. Knowledge of the GoGreen definition for green conservation and green parameters, and the Green Decision-Making Model (DMM). Supported by the module ***Leadership in Green Conservation***
2. Familiarity of the 10 Agents of Deterioration for Cultural Heritage supported by the suggested pre-reading

Additionally, pre-requisite knowledge is supported by the recommended pre-readings detailed below.

RECOMMENDED PRE-READINGS

Canadian Conservation Institute (2025) Agents of Deterioration. Government of Canada.

Available at: <https://www.canada.ca/en/conservation-institute/services/agents-deterioration.html>

MISSION STATEMENT

To promote informed and adaptive decision-making for cultural heritage through knowledge of green preventive conservation strategies, tools, and material sensitivities.

DESCRIPTION

Determining Material Sensitivities and Green Decision-Making introduces tools for identifying and evaluating material sensitivity and stability to support greener approaches in preventive conservation. Proposed topics encourage the development of interdisciplinary skills in material science and cultural heritage conservation.

Learners are introduced to tools including damage functions and the HERle a digital decision-support platform to assess environmental impacts and risks for cultural heritage. Using these tools, they develop sustainable, context-specific preventive conservation strategies that consider climate, resources, human health and well-being, and cultural heritage.

At the end of the module, learners will have the opportunity to put their new knowledge and skills into practice by developing a preventive conservation approach for their personal or local context and advocating for its implementation, developing practical leadership skills in green conservation.

LEARNING GOALS AND OUTCOMES

Main Goal Support learners to make green(er) decisions for preventive conservation using knowledge of material science of cultural heritage and tools for green decision-making.

Subsidiary Goals

- Develop awareness of how the environment influences the physical and chemical stability of materials in cultural heritage objects.
- Build competence in using diagnostic tools and analytical techniques to identify and interpret environmental risks to cultural heritage.
- Foster interdisciplinary understanding by linking material science, conservation, and sustainability to inform the decision-making process.
- Reflect on preventive conservation approaches and decisions and identify how they support long-term preservation while aligning with the green parameters.

By the end of this module,

Learning Outcomes

1. **(Evaluation)** Evaluate the sustainability impact of preventive conservation practices, in relation to waste management, energy consumption, environmental pollution, human health, and inclusion.
2. **(Analysis)** Analyse the extent to which one's preventive conservation actions conform to green conservation criteria and identify opportunities for improvement.
3. **(Application)** Apply diagnostic tools (e.g., HERle and damage functions) to evaluate how environmental parameters such as relative humidity, temperature, and light affect the stability, reactivity, and vulnerability of organic and inorganic cultural heritage, thereby supporting context-specific, risk-based greener preventive conservation strategies.
4. **(Communication)** Negotiate and advocate for greener preventive conservation strategies through assessing risks using diagnostic tools, such as HERle and damage functions.

RECOMMENDED READINGS

Visit the GoGreen Zenodo for the full module bibliography.

- Bickersteth, J.** (2016). IIC and ICOM-CC 2014 Declaration on Environmental Guidelines. *Studies in Conservation*, 61(sup1), 12–17. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2016.1166018>
- Bujok, S., Bridarolli, A., Łukomski, M., & Bratasz, Ł.** (2024). Reconsidering Museums' Climate and Seasonal Adjustment for Vulnerable Artifacts. *Studies in Conservation*, 69(sup1), 18–24. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2024.2375162>
- CIMAM.** (n.d.). *The BIZOT Green Protocol*. CIMAM. Retrieved 22 July 2025, from <https://www.cimam.org/sustainability-and-ecology-museum-practice/bizot-green-protocol/>
- Cosaert, A., & Beltran, V. L. (Eds.)** (2022). *Tools for the analysis of collection environments: Lessons learned and future development; research report*. Getty Conservation Institute.
- Dalla Mora, T., De Vivo, M. A., Scarpa, M., & Peron, F.** (2025). Critical Review of the Application of the Principal International Standards and Guidelines on Indoor Microclimates for the Preventive Conservation of Cultural Heritage. *Sustainability*, 17(3), 1189. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su17031189>
- Kramer, R. P., Schellen, H. L., & Van Schijndel, A. W. M.** (2016). Impact of ASHRAE's museum climate classes on energy consumption and indoor climate fluctuations: Full-scale measurements in museum Hermitage Amsterdam. *Energy and Buildings*, 130, 286–294. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.08.016>
- Kupczak, A., Jędrychowski, M., Strojecki, M., Krzemień, L., Bratasz, Ł., Łukomski, M., & Kozłowski, R.** (2018). HERle: A Web-Based Decision-Supporting Tool for Assessing Risk of Physical Damage Using Various Failure Criteria. *Studies in Conservation*, 63(sup1), 151–155. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2018.1504447>
- Quabeck, N.** (2023). Reviewing processes, relaxing parameters: On-collection climate research at the Kunstsammlung Nordrhein-Westfalen. *ICOM-CC Valencia*. <https://www.icom-cc-publications-online.org/5596/Reviewing-processes-relaxing-parameters--On-collection-climate-research-at-the-Kunstsammlung-Nordrhein-Westfalen>
- Saunders, D.** (2022). A Methodology for Modelling Preservation, Access and Sustainability. *Studies in Conservation*, 67, 245–252. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2022.2055933>
- Strlič, M., Thickett, D., Taylor, J., & Cassar, M.** (2013). Damage functions in heritage science. *Studies in Conservation*, 58(2), 80–87. <https://doi.org/10.1179/2047058412Y.0000000073>
- Thickett, D.** (2018). Frontiers of Preventive Conservation. *Studies in Conservation*, 63(sup1), 262–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2018.1504455>

Thickett, D. (2023). Practical Use of Damage Functions for Environmental Preventive Conservation and Sustainability—Examples from Naturally Ventilated Buildings. *Heritage*, 6(3), 2633–2649. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6030139>

Thickett, D., Emmerson, N., Larsen, R., Odlyha, M., & Watkinson, D. (2022). Analysing Objects to Tailor Environmental Preventive Conservation. *Heritage*, 6(1), 212–235. <https://doi.org/10.3390/heritage6010011>

Thickett, D., Mélinis, A., & Shah, B. (2024). Measurement of Sorption Isotherms to Guide Mixed Display of Archaeological Iron, Bone, and Glass. *Materials*, 17(23), 5934. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ma17235934>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2024). Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: Methodological guidance. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>

European Commission. Joint Research Centre. (2024). Safe and sustainable by design chemicals and materials: Methodological guidance. Publications Office. <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2760/28450>

SUPPLEMENTARY READINGS

Camuffo, D. (2023), Microclimate for Cultural Heritage: Conservation and Restoration of Indoor and Outdoor Monuments: Conservation, Restoration, and Maintenance of Indoor and Outdoor Monuments, Elsevier

Grau-Bové, J., & Strlič, M. (2013). Fine particulate matter in indoor cultural heritage: a literature review. *Heritage Science*, 1(1), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1186/2050-7445-1-8>

Saunders, D. (2025). Sustainability in Museum Lighting. In Á. F. Perles-Ivars, L. Fuster-López, & E. Bosco (Eds), *Collection Care* (pp. 71–87). Springer Nature Switzerland. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-85655-6_7

Taylor, J., & Beltran, V. L. (Eds.). (2023). *Technical Note 10: Considerations for the process of managing collection environments*. In Getty Conservation Institute.

Thickett, D. (2018). Frontiers of Preventive Conservation. *Studies in Conservation*, 63(sup1), 262–267. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00393630.2018.1504455>

DETERMINING MATERIAL SENSITIVITIES AND GREEN DECISION-MAKING

THEME	TOPICS	DESCRIPTION	LEARNING OUTCOMES	ACTIVITIES + ASSESSMENTS
Preventive Conservation and Sustainable Development	<i>Impact of Preventive Conservation on Sustainability</i>	Explores the impact of preventive conservation on the four impact areas highlighted in the definition of green conservation and parameters.	Evaluate the sustainability impact of preventive conservation practices, in relation to waste management, energy consumption, environmental pollution, human health, and inclusion.	Assessment: Choose a case study of a preventive conservation strategy or approach to apply the green conservation definition and parameters and discuss how it affects the four impact areas (i.e., climate, use of resources, human health and well-being, and cultural heritage). Reflect on the challenges of this approach in relation to sustainable development and suggest how it could be improved or adapted for future practice.
Green Decision-Making Tools & Frameworks	<i>Tools, Frameworks, and Guidelines for Green Decision-Making</i>	Introduces tools and frameworks available for green decision-making in preventive conservation. Topic provides an overview for the following tools from the GoGreen project: HERle, Damage Functions, DSA App.	Analyse the extent to which one's preventive conservation actions conform to green conservation criteria and identify opportunities for improvement.	Activity: Deep dive into a tool or framework and in a presentation provide a summary of its applications and emphasise how insights from the tool or framework contribute to evolving traditional strategies toward more sustainable, green(er) practices. Activity: Identify and describe personal preventive conservation practices, then research one traditional method and one greener alternative related to the same area. If in pairs, share findings and collaboratively compare the two in terms of techniques, environmental/resource impact, effectiveness, and practical challenges. Evaluate how personal measures align with green conservation principles and parameters and identify ways they could be improved to be greener. Reflect on the potential benefits and feasibility of adopting greener strategies in your own context.
	<i>Comparing Measurements to Models</i>	Through case studies, reviews how the green decision-making tools and frameworks predict object behaviour and how it compares to reality. Topic considers limitations for application in preventive conservation decision-making.		
Analysing Objects: Composition, Rate of Deterioration, and Preservation	<i>Inorganic Objects: Metals</i>	The following topics explore how assessing an object's material composition, deterioration rate, and preservation state supports preventive conservation planning. Each topic focuses on a specific material group and demonstrates how green tools and frameworks can be applied to evaluate object stability and risks for decision-making in preventive conservation. Learners apply these tools to case examples to develop sustainable preventive strategies.	Apply diagnostic tools (e.g., HERle and damage functions) to evaluate how environmental parameters such as relative humidity, temperature, and light affect the stability, reactivity, and vulnerability of organic and inorganic cultural heritage, thereby supporting context-specific, risk-based greener preventive conservation strategies.	Assessment: Utilise a green decision-making assessment tool on a case study and present your findings. Discuss how material composition, deterioration rates, and preservation state influences preventive conservation strategies and analyse its impact on the following four areas: climate, resource use, human health and well-being, and cultural heritage.
	<i>Inorganic Objects: Ceramic, Stone, and Glass</i>			
	<i>Organic Objects: Paper, Wood, and Canvas</i>			
	<i>Complex Cases, Adaptation and Limitations of Measurements and Tools</i>	Introduces adaptations and limitations of measurements, tools and frameworks for complex cases and personal contexts. Considering how object individuality may impact preventive strategies.		
Green(er) Preventive Strategies	<i>Green(er) Approaches for Preventive Conservation</i>	Explores green(er) approaches for preventive conservation through the review and analysis of case studies	Negotiate and advocate for greener preventive conservation strategies through assessing risks using diagnostic tools, such as HERle and damage functions	Assessment: Building on previous work, explore green(er) approaches to preventive conservation and design and present a preventive conservation strategy. Compare previous preventive approaches with proposed new strategy in terms of the green conservation definition and parameters. Consider various forms of communication strategies to create a proposal for implementing strategy.
	<i>Practical Application</i>	Provides learners with the opportunity to apply green conservation principles to their personal and local contexts to develop and present their strategy in an accessible format, advocating for sustainable practices within their sphere of influence.		

DISCLAIMER

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or Horizon Europe. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

AUTHORS AND CONTRIBUTORS

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